

Linguistic and cultural study of the language of advertising (on the material of the English and Karakalpak languages)

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Abstract:

Translation of advertising today is singled out as a completely separate area of translator's activity, which requires from a specialist not only an ideal knowledge of the stylistic subtleties and cultural nuances of Karakalpak and English languages, but also a clear understanding of the consumers' psychology.

Key words: linguacultural, advertising, study, original, commercials, stereotypes, phenomenology.

Advertising can be seen as an external reflection of culture. Each country speaks to itself through hundreds of thirty-second commercials that offer a look at everyday things that surround a person through the prism of culture. Often the differences come down to simple stereotypes. There is an opinion that American advertising is unpretentious, English is distinguished by its humor, German is intrusive, and French is refined and original. Advertising text is a literary form that reflects the values of a specific target audience. Advertising text as an object of linguistic research has been studied in the last decade by domestic and foreign researchers in accordance with the principles of the linguoculturological approach. The language of advertising is considered by them as a special linguistic structure that develops according to its own laws, as it pursues non-linguistic goals. This approach allows us to consider the diversity of discourses through the prism of linguistic mentality and national values, studies the national and cultural specific rules for organizing speech communication.

The purpose of this study is to study some of the linguocultural aspects that determine English advertising texts. Material and methods. As a material, we studied some samples of English-language advertising using the methods of phenomenologization and conceptualization (analysis of psychological, scientific, methodological, linguoculturological literature on the research problem).

When adapting advertising, slogans and names, it is necessary to take into account the peculiarities of the perception of meanings for a particular audience.

And in the Karakalpak language, the words of advertising do not matter too much, because in Karakalpakstan they also use English words, but this does not mean

that Karakalpak does not use it at all. For example, Karakalpak advertising words are usually used in national dishes or shop names: Turkistan, Dosliq kanali, Pana-Milk...

It is important that the text conveys meaning and mood. But if the original marketers use various tricks to improve the perception of the text, then it becomes more difficult to translate it. There are a huge number of such tricks: puns and puns, rhyming, consonance of individual words or double meanings of phrases. If they are, then 100% accurate translation becomes impossible. The translator can only get as close as possible to the original presentation. Some experts do this very well.

Results. The study of English advertising texts showed that from a functional point of view, advertising texts combine the implementation of two impact functions. This is the function of the impact of the language, implemented with the help of the entire arsenal of linguistic means of expression and the function of mass communication, implemented using special media technologies that are characteristic of a particular media [1]. Advertising should form and consolidate in the mind of the recipient stable stereotypes of lifestyle, thinking, morality, which is an integral part of the formation of public consciousness [2, p. 133].

To achieve the greatest efficiency of the above-mentioned functions of influence in English advertising texts, the same compositional type prevails: “beginning” + information block + slogan + reference data. If we talk about the tact of English advertising texts, then we can recognize the type of "initiation - information block + slogan". At the same time, it should be noted that the composition of English advertising texts is more strict, since the sequence “beginning + information block + slogan + reference data” is the standard, and deviation from it is more related to single use than in the case of numerous Russian texts, where this sequence is not always observed [3].

Having considered and compared the use of phonosemantic and lexical means of expression in various advertising slogans, we can conclude that in English-language advertising, alliteration, that is, the repetition of homogeneous consonants, which gives the literary text a special sound and intonation expressiveness, turned out to be the most frequent phonosemantic component [3]. For example, in an advertisement for watches from one of the leading Swiss companies Tissot: “Trust only in true values. T collection. Tissot Watches. Swiss Watches Since 1853.” / “I believe only in true values T-collection. Tissot watch. Swiss watches since 1853” – the first phrase “Trust only in true values” calls to believe only in true values, one of which is the company’s products [4, p. 17]. The capital T logo of Tissot, whose name begins and ends with the letter “t”, serves as the basis for the alliteration of the consonant /t/ in a number of words: trust, true, T-collection, Tissot. A similar role is played by the letter /s/ in the

words trust, Tissot, values, watches, Swiss and since. In order to increase the impact on the recipient and emphasize the value of the advertised products, the year of foundation of the company is indicated - 1853, and the country where the watches are made - Switzerland.

Speaking about the English-language advertising discourse, it is worth noting that here most often the lexical units of evaluative semantics are represented by verbs. In the advertising slogan of the online bank: "Your money needs an Ally". / "Your money needs an ally," the verb "need", emphasizes an urgent need [5, p. 351]. With the help of this language unit, advertisers emphasize the importance of the bank, i.e. they give it a positive rating. Advertising slogans often contain the words: good (good), better (best), free (available), great (great), sure (undoubted), new (new) and there is practically no negatively colored vocabulary [6, p. 423].

Rhyme in advertising is also a very common method aimed at different audiences. Rhyme is a special kind of sound repetition, that is, the repetition of parts of words or words in different parts of poems or utterances. This is a common technique in the use of English-language advertisements. Previously, in the United States, advertising looked like a performance by hawkers who composed their own advertising tongue twisters or jokes, thereby advertising their product [7, p. 120].

An example of a male English rhyme is: "The best part of waking up is Folger's in your cup" - an advertisement for 'Folger' coffee (up - cup); "You'll be lovelier each day with fabulous pink Camay" - soap advertisement (day - Camay).

An example of female rhyme can be seen in the following advertisements: "Drinka pinta milka day" - advertisement of the 'National milk publicity council' (drinka - pinta - milka rhyme is achieved through the use of assonance - repetition of the stressed sound /I/ and unstressed /ə/; "Get fresh "Stay strong. Hair feels fresher, stronger, for longer."

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